

Availability of Open Access Metadata from Open Journals – A case study in DOAJ and Crossref

Davide Brembilla (0000-0002-9481-5053)¹, Chiara Catizone (0000-0003-2445-2426)¹ and Giulia Venditti (0000-0001-7696-7574)¹

¹Department of Philology and Italian studies, Master Course in DHDK, Bologna University

Abstract

Purpose: *With the spread of data in the public domain, Open Access and Open Science practices are becoming central to the scholarly community. They can improve the transparency and robustness of the analysis of science, improve science policy decision-making, and increase the discoverability of scientific articles. The databases containing Open information about scientific articles have, thus, grown more and more important. This inquiry is aimed at studying how metadata of Open Access articles are treated by the DOAJ and Crossref, evaluating the management of data linked to articles (references) and trying to understand how aggregators and publishers share information and individuate variables influencing this behaviour.*

Approach: *Our research involves the articles from the Open Access journals listed in DOAJ and their data indexed on Crossref. We scouted the presence of identifiers of the articles, their presence on Crossref and the availability of their reference lists, along with the entities responsible for their DOIs' specification. This analysis was carried out by using DOAJ's public data dumps and Crossref's API.*

Findings: *Our research's main findings are: a) most articles from DOAJ have also been found on Crossref, that more than half of these articles' records on Crossref have reference lists, and the items of these reference list about almost 70% have a DOI, half of the times asserted by their publisher. However, there are significant differences depending on the journals' geographical origin, their size in terms of DOIs and their research fields, that this study will also deepen.*

Originality: *This project touches on the completeness of data in the DOAJ, as well as its role within the Open Access community. Having a clearer picture of Open Access Publishing is important, as it allows us to identify good practices or flaws in this field. Empirical studies in this niche are lacking and are (usually) focused on smaller issues, rather than the wider picture.*

Limitations: *This study is limited in scope to the data available on DOAJ. Problems in the original data (e.g., DOI duplicates and non-standard dates) may have influenced the results, as well as the unbalanced presence of DOIs in the fields evaluated.*

Keywords: *DOAJ, Crossref, Bibliometrics, Scientometrics, Open Science, Open Access*

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context

With the growth of the scholarly community's presence on the internet, the web has been a primary factor in making research discoverable and accessible. Scholars have been trying to maximise the advantages given to science by online tools with movements such as Open Science and the adoption of Open Access methodologies (Woelfle et al., 2011), trying to circumvent the barriers placed by publishers to science.

By making available to the public articles in this way, the shape of the research community has been changed significantly, and mapping this change is a complicated task requiring multiple efforts.

1.2 State of the Art

Multiple studies have been laid out to map the direction of Open Access Publishing (Piwowar et al., 2018), pointing out its importance and challenges. In addition, several institutions have sprung up to support Open Access publications, playing an increasingly important role in the research life-cycle. Meanwhile, DOAJ and Crossref have set themselves apart as providers of data for most of the bibliometrics research about Open Access articles.

The Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) is actually the most recognised and most authoritative list of scholarly, peer-reviewed, fully Open Access journals. More than 17,500 journals are listed in it, making it one of the biggest aggregators of Open Scholarship metadata.

An example of the type of analysis that is possible to obtain from the articles in the DOAJ is provided by Ghane et al. (2020), whose analysis is aimed at the evaluation of the correlation between APC (Article Processing Charges) and the impact of articles. Journal metadata is also useful to investigate the transparency of publishers, as it was done in a study about Elsevier's journals by Jahn et al. (2021). A very interesting study about the trends in Open Access publishing is Piwowar et al. (2019), which employs data from Unpaywall (<https://unpaywall.org/>), a browser extension that allows users to find Open Access versions of articles, projecting the trends of scholarly publishing in the future. Martín-Martín et al. (2018a) studied the availability of Open Access articles. Inquiries about the Open Access publication world have been carried out on the geographical distribution of OAJ, such as for India in Panda (2021).

Crossref "makes research outputs easy to find, cite, link, and assess"¹. It is a not-for-profit membership organization considered as the most successful example of cooperation across the publishing community for enabling persistent cross-publisher citation linking in online academic journals. The metadata is preserved for the scholarly record, and it is also made available across a range of interfaces and formats so that the community can use it and build tools with it.

Chudlarský and Dvořák (2020) pointed out that the data from Crossref is still too little to substitute other services, but the number of total records kept growing in size; indeed, next year we have Eck (2021) showing us how Crossref's data availability keeps growing in completeness. About reference lists – apart from the many, seminal, theoretical articles such as Shotton (2013) – critical studies have

¹cf. <https://www.crossref.org/>

shown their importance in the development of science. Ahlgren et al. (2018) used citation data to highlight the impact of citations on discoverability and citability of data; Piwowar and Vision (2013) specifically showed a growing advantage for open citations of articles. Visser et al. (2021) compared the distribution of citation data across multiple aggregators, including Crossref. Related articles to our study are also Gatten (2010), which studied the accuracy of reference lists, and Cioffi et al. (2021), focused on the correctness of DOIs and citations from Crossref and in COCI.

Open Access metadata is still a difficult problem for Journals and Open Access Indexers, as Cheby (2016) shows in her study. While OA metadata is required to make OA articles discoverable, it is possible to produce and distribute OA metadata for non-OA material. To make metadata interoperable, many standards and crosswalks have been established. While various schemes and protocols appear to be developing towards prospective standards, there appears to be a considerable misunderstanding over who creates metadata and the publisher's role in coordinating metadata creation and distribution.

Even though the DOAJ follows strict OA metadata standards, it does not produce metadata itself like commercial distributors. As a result, metadata creation necessitates specialized expertise as well as close coordination and communication among library experts, programmers, publishers, and distributors.

1.3 Objectives

The purpose of our research is to investigate, through a data-driven approach, the involvement of publishers and aggregators in the making of available and reliable metadata for Open Access Journals and their articles. And, on the other hand, we also wanted to measure how important Crossref is to complete metadata as well as to make articles' reference lists accessible to a wider audience of researchers, starting from Digital Object Identifier (DOI) stored in DOAJ (Ghane et al., 2020)(Piwowar and Vision, 2013).

A DOI is a Persistent Identifier that refers to a digital resource, in our case the products of a scholarly effort. A DOI is a critical component in creating a scholarly environment that is consistent with its practices, optimising the findability of resources for research purposes. DOIs refer to multiple types of objects, from articles to software, from datasets to presentations, and they can be registered by agencies.

Metadata (data about data) is a very useful resource to improve the indexability and findability of research products (both final and intermediate). DOAJ and Crossref provide article metadata; in particular, Crossref also stores, if indicated, the article's reference list.

Reference lists are also important to enhance the value of an article, as it indicates the resources used to create a scholarly article and to evaluate whether the research was on point. In this context, Crossref created an algorithm to match reference titles with their DOI, if present. The responsibility for assigning a DOI to the reference is held as 'DOI-asserted-by' in Crossref's metadata and it could be either Crossref itself or the publisher of citing article. Studies from Crossref suggested that in 2019 43% of reference lists on Crossref lacked a publisher-asserted DOI.

1.4 Research question

Given this context, we asked ourselves these research questions:

- **RQ1:** How many articles published in the open access journals in DOAJ are included in Crossref?
- **RQ2:** How many of these records include information about their reference lists?
- **RQ3:** How many references have a DOI specified?
- **RQ4:** How many of these DOIs have been specified by the publishers? And how many have been specified by Crossref?

In this research paper, we found that articles in DOAJ journals are usually on Crossref; however, there are significant differences in the distribution that may be connected to the unbalanced distribution of resources and know-how through different axes of analysis (countries, research field). This difference is even more apparent in the availability of reference lists. Biases can also be observed in the behaviour of publishers indicating the reference DOIs and the role of Crossref. In the development of our research, we found that DOAJ data has inconsistencies that could be addressed, also in cooperation with Crossref, to ensure good metadata for all articles.

The paper is organised as follows: in section II an overview of tools and methods used in our research. In section III we show the obtained results through an in-deep description, supported by visual representation. Finally, in section IV discussion on obtained results is made, introducing topics for future work and research limits.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGIES

2.1 Subjects

The subjects of our study are scientific journals' articles published in Open Access and their references' metadata.

Specifically, we chose DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journal), as the source of our articles. As presented in our State of the Art, this directory's importance in scientometrics research is also highlighted by the multiple inquiries – using DOAJ data and other information from the scholarly domain – made over time, that were aimed at analyzing distinct types of Open Access. DOAJ has been active since the '90s, and – according to Laakso et al. (2011) – it is a suitable operationalisation of the target population.

To gather data on article references we exploited an indexer – i.e., Crossref – providing the reference lists of each article – if available – and the main entities in charge of registering DOIs of scholarly publications – the publisher or Crossref through a crawler-alike algorithm.

As it has been assessed in previous studies, Crossref makes research outputs easier to find, cite, link, and assess. Crossref connects millions of items from a variety of content types. When members register their content on Crossref, it collects both bibliographic and non-bibliographic metadata, which is processed so that connections can be made between publications, people, organizations, and other associated outputs (Hendricks et al., 2020).

2.2 *Materials*

The materials used are discerned into 3 main categories:

- Downloaded data sets
- Data sets resulting from our manipulations
- Software auto-produced and some already available tools in open source

2.2.1 *Downloaded data sets*

The original materials of our research come respectively from DOAJ's public data dumps and Crossref's REST-API responses.

DOAJ's dumps were simply downloaded from the browser and we decided to keep both articles' and journal dumps as we believed they could come useful to us if combined.

The Journals metadata is licensed under a CC-BY-SA 4.0 License, while articles metadata's copyrights and related rights for article metadata were waived via CC0 1.0 Universal (CC0) Public Domain Dedication.

2.2.2 *Created data sets*

This second step consisted of the creation of three data sets, each one stemming from the one previously downloaded/made, until we reached a final form, which would provide us with computable data to perform analysis of the overall data Brembilla et al. (2022a).

The group started experimenting with some queries on Crossref and explored the DOAJ's articles dump to get an overall understanding of the data in there.

At this point we decided that the starting point of our experiments would have been the articles' dump by DOAJ, we assessed its size to be 22 GB, therefore the first researcher extracted the necessary information. All data sets contain canonical data — textual and numerical — selected in compliance with our study's information needs to address its research objectives.²

1. 20220521_la_chouffe_clean_articles_v_0_0_1.tar.gz

is the first data set created and it stores: a) the DOI of each article; b) the publication year; c) the ISSN codes of the journal it belongs to. The decompressed file format is *.json*.

Template:

²For more information about Canonical datatypes <https://docs.openclinica.com/3-1-technical-documents/openclinica-item-data-specifications/openclinica-item-data-specifications-canonical-datatypes/>

```
{ "DOI":  
  { "year": "XXXX",  
    "issns": [ "XXXX-XXX", "XXXX-XXXX" ] },  
  "DOI":  
    { "year": "XXXX",  
      "issns": [ "XXXX-XXX", "XXXX-XXXX" ] },  
  ..... }
```

Licensing waived via CC0 1.0 Universal (CC0) Public Domain Dedication

2. 20220521_la_chouffe_articles_populated_v_0_0_1.ta has been created by adding information acquired through Crossref's REST API. This data frame expands DOAJ articles' metadata with a) several references; b) reference list (with information about assertion); c) entity responsible for the assertion of DOI; d) presence of the article in Crossref; e) articles type. When decompressed these files are provided in *.json* format.

Template:

```
{ "DOI":  
  "ISSNS": {  
    "DOI": {  
      "crossref": \X",  
      "year": "XXXX",  
      "reference": {  
        "ref1": {  
          "DOI": "DOI",  
          "DOI-asserted-by": "someone"  
        },  
        "ref2": { ... }  
      }  
    }  
  }  
  subject:"SSH or STM"  
  type: "journal-article or volume or..."  
  ..... }
```

Licensing waived via CC0 1.0 Universal (CC0) Public Domain Dedication

3. 20220521_la_chouffe_aggregated_data_v_0_0_1.pkl is the final data set used to perform analysis on the gathered data. It stores a) ISSNs; b) DOIs; c) DOIs' presence (1,0) used for counts; d) DOI presence in Crossref (1,0) used for counts; e) presence of a reference list (1,0) used for counts; f) the total number of references in each article's the list; g) total number of DOIs asserted by the publisher in reference lists; h) the total number of references' DOIs asserted by Crossref; i) the total number of articles without a DOI; j) publication year; k) country; l) subject, m) article type.

Licensing: Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0) license

4. **Software:** The software created for this research is divided into multiple components, each dedicated to a specific task concerning data gathering or manipulations. The programming language used for coding the software is Python version 3.9 or later releases Brembilla et al. (2022b).

For cleaning the DOAJ articles' metadata we developed a first software called `batches_cleaner.py` that copies the necessary information from the DOAJ's article metadata into a new data frame; then we developed `multithread_populating.py` and `main.py` to query Crossref and combine the response data with what we already had from articles metadata, `stats.py` creates CSV files from the outputs of `main`.

After this phase, we observed that some valuable information such as the country of provenance of journals and their subject were missing from our data. To fill this gap in our data we started manipulating the second dump downloaded from DOAJ: the journals' metadata, `journal_cleaner.py` was the software dedicated to this last task.

Finally, `populator.py` is the last script used to combine the CSV files and the files from `stats` with journals' metadata.

Additional code – for plotting the visualizations in data analysis – is stored in the notebook `data_viz.ipynb`.

Software is licensed under MIT license.

2.3 Research design

Our research is a data-driven analysis, aimed at describing the dynamics behind the assertion of references' DOIs on OA indexers. We follow Open Access and FAIR principles, to allow other researchers to reproduce and replicate our study. Therefore, all the data we started from as well as the products of our research are freely available to third parties.

As stated in our introduction multiple studies have already covered the topic of OA publishing, but we feel the need to add a – hopefully beneficial – point of view to this field, focusing on references, the involvement of publishers in making them discoverable and the ability of Crossref's algorithm to infer them when missing.

The final set of variables – i.e., the columns of our final data set – needed for the data analysis phase is the following:

Variable	Value Example	Media Type	Utility
issns	1234-5678	categorical	Used to identify printed, electronic, or serial publications, serving us as the DOAJ journals identifier
DOI	10.1000/182	categorical	Digital Object Identifier used for articles
DOI-num	1	numerical	Used to keep the number of DOIs when grouping the data frame by other variables
on-crossref	0/1	numerical	Used to assert the presence of a DOI on Crossref
reference	0/1	numerical	Used to assert the presence of a reference list in articles metadata on Crossref
asserted-by-cr	count	numerical	Total count of references in the list with DOI asserted by Crossref
asserted-by-pub	count	numerical	Total count of references in the list with DOI asserted by publishers
ref-undefined	count	numerical	Undefined/missing DOIs
ref-num	count	numerical	Total number of references in the list
year	YYYY	ordinal	Publication year of the given article
country	Country label ISO alpha-2	categorical	Country of the provenance of the journal
subject	Library of Congress Classification of subjects	categorical	STM — SSH
type	Classification given by Crossref	categorical	Resource typology (e.g., journal article, volume, report, etc.

Table 1. Variables used in our final dataset

Both ISSNs and DOIs have been employed in our research, allowing us to group and distinguish articles belonging to the same journal.

The numerical variables used here are the ones responsible for answering our research questions. The “DOI-num” and “on-crossref” variables have been employed in answering RQ1. For the second research question, we used the total number of articles on Crossref again and compared it with “reference” – the number of DOIs having a reference list. RQ3 focuses on the number of references having a specified DOI, using “ref-num” and “ref-undefined” and their difference, representing defined articles. Finally, for RQ4 we computed the proportions of references’ DOIs asserted by Crossref, by the citing article publisher and not asserted at all.

“Year”, “country” and “subject” worked for us as independent variables, adding granularity to our analysis. We decided to start the analysis by giving a general overview of the data involved in answering each research question. And go granular as we add independent variables to our measurements. “Year” adds a temporal dimension to the inquired phenomena, “country” adds geographical references to it, and “subject” as it has been often used in literature to divide journals into domains and look at their different behaviours.

2.3.1 FAIR and OPEN principles

As we stated at the beginning of this section, we followed FAIR and OPEN principles when managing our data.

All data sets and software have been described with metadata stored in two Turtle files. One for describing the final data set and the other for describing the software.

```
@prefix dcterms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>.
@prefix dct: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>.
@prefix dctype: <http://purl.org/dc/dcmitype/>.
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema>.
@prefix schema: <https://schema.org/>.
@prefix wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6562909>
  a dct:Dataset;
  dcterms:title "La Chouffe Dataset"@en;
  dcterms:title "Dataset La Chouffe"@it;
  dcterms:creator <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7696-7574>;
  dcterms:creator <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2445-2426>;
  dcterms:creator <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9481-5053>;
  dcterms:subject "Scientometrics, DOAJ, Crossref";
  dcterms:subject wd:Q1227538;
  dcterms:subject wd:Q5188229;
  dcterms:issued "2022-05-21";
  dcterms:license <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>;
  dcterms:description "A dataset containing information from the DOAJ and Crossref used in performing research about the availability of data from one another. Contains 3 folders; one with the clean batch that was used to create the populated one in populated_output; the last one contains csv files with aggregated information about the articles. Please refer to https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6491625 for more details."

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7696-7574>
  a schema:Person;
  rdfs:label "Venditti, Giulia";
  schema:affiliation wd:Q56459946.

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2445-2426>
  a schema:Person;
  rdfs:label "Catizone, Chiara";
  schema:affiliation wd:Q56459946.

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9481-5053>
  a schema:Person;
  rdfs:label "Brembilla, Davide";
  schema:affiliation wd:Q56459946.
```

Figure 1. Screenshot of our .ttl file .

The vocabularies used are Dublin Core, DCAT, RDF schema, Schema.org and WikiData. The data sets are described as a whole, as they are stored on Zenodo as a folder having a single DOI, additionally, we describe ourselves as dc:creators of this material.

Findable

F1	Metadata and Data are assigned a DOI as a persistent unique identifier
F2	Use of DCAT and Dublin Core as a framework for describing our material
F3	Metadata are connected to the data through an identifier
F4	Metadata is indexed on Zenodo

Accessible

A1	No specialized, nor proprietary tools are needed for accessing data
A1.1	Data downloadable through HTTP protocol
A1.2	No authentication needed as no sensitive data is involved
A2	We specify reference studies and guarantee to be available to anyone for further specifications or to provide backup data

Interoperable

I1	Use of Dublin Core
I2	The vocabularies used to describe data sets are documented and resolvable using globally unique and persistent identifiers
I3	Meaningful links between data in the Turtle file

Reusable

R1	Files description in Turtle file
R1.1	Metadata and Data is licensed with a CC0 licence (when possible)
R1.2	We provide a clear history of the origin of our data in this report, the DMP and the Protocol
R1.3	We use domain-relevant metadata such as Dublin Core

Table 2. FAIR Principles in our data set

Openness in terms of freedom of access, use, modify, and share for any purpose is guaranteed by licenses such as CC-BY-SA and CC-0, that force openness on our data set; on the other hand, we use MIT License for our software as it has high license compatibility – including copyleft licenses³.

The work is provided as a whole and downloadable through the internet in compressed format. Decompressed files' formats – i.e., JSON, CSV, and PICKLE – are also compliant with the Open Definition and metadata is provided in .ttl format – a machine-readable format.

Original Data comes from trustworthy sources such as Crossref and DOAJ. DOAJ is committed to increasing “visibility, accessibility, reputation, usage and impact of quality, peer-reviewed, Open Access scholarly research journals globally, regardless of discipline, geography or language”⁴.

Crossref states that “[...] metadata is provided to us by our members, and we don't curate or clean up the metadata in any way. We do insert metadata into outputs such as DOI matches for citations, and recursive relationships, and flag those pieces as being inserted by Crossref in our metadata outputs.” Data coming from these two different sources have been merged and integrated in a way to make it prone to operationalization.

Long-term preservation is guaranteed by the backups of the research materials and results in the local storage of researchers' machines. The research group also intends to remain available for further clarification on our work, if needed.

2.4 Procedure

The procedure undertaken in this study is split into 3 main steps:

1. Data gathering
2. Data visualization and Analysis
3. Data publishing

When gathering data, we started by downloading open-source article's metadata made available by DOAJ. The downloaded file was in *tar.gz* format and once decompressed it was structured as a directory of *JSON* files weighting several gigabytes. As we believed size could become a problem in later phases we decided to keep only ISSNs, DOIs and publication year of articles as initial data.

The software employed in this first cleaning is `batches_cleaner.py` and the output file is the data set `20220727_la_chouffe_cleaned_datasets_v1_1.tar.gz`, which weights 87.6 MB. The script (which requires having python 3 installed) can be run from a personal computer's terminal with the commands:

```
py -m batches_cleaner doaj_article_data_[date generated] #windows
python3 -m batches_cleaner doaj_article_data_[date generated] #macos
```

³cfr. <https://opendefinition.org/od/2.1/en/> for a definition of Open.

⁴<https://doaj.org/about/our-mission>

Starting from this first output we launch the software `main.py` from the terminal with commands:

```
py -m main [path to files] #windows
python3 -m main [path to files] #macos
```

This software uses a multi-threading method to send synchronous requests to Crossref's API. We used this approach as the expected time for downloading all the necessary information was estimated to be 1 or more weeks.

As we started getting the first batches populated with Crossref's responses, we started saving them with `stats.py` and have a look at this data in search for mistakes. We noticed that this data alone was not saying much about the actual situation on DOIs assertion, hence we also cleaned journals metadata with `journal_cleaner.py`, keeping their ISSNs codes, country codes and the array describing the journal subjects conforming to the Library of Congress Classification⁵. This additional information is aggregated with the rest of the data by `populator.py`, the component in charge of creating the data frame used for the analysis.

Once all the needed data was retrieved and our information needs were fulfilled, we printed the description of the data set and plotted some visualizations using Python's Plotly library.

We iterated twice over our research questions with the commands:

```
df.describe #for describing the whole df
df[df["column-name"] == value].describe()
```

In this way, we gathered the count, mean and standard deviation of each numerical value present in the data frame and decided to focus on the subset of articles having a reference list.

We iterated twice over our research questions. The first time we limited the visualizations to pie-charts showing the main characteristics of the articles' distributions in Crossref. As we finished this phase we observed these first results to decide how to proceed.

We decided to add country, time and subjects as additional independent variables. Here we exploited line charts, histograms and multiple kinds of bar charts to look for correlations and trends in our variables.

The following stage of our research consisted of the discussion of our results and the publication of our material.

3 RESULTS

For our results, we refer to:

- Continents as they have been converted by `pycountry_converter` from their countries (following the classification given by Wikipedia) using the `convert_continent_code_to_continent_name` method.

⁵We recommend to perform this last step together with the first one instead.

- Research fields as they have been indexed by DOAJ, using the Library of Congress Classification and grouped as follows:
 - **SSH** (Social Sciences and Humanities): B, C, D, E, F, G, H, L, M, N, P
 - **STM** (Science, Technology and Medicine): R, S, T

3.1 DOAJ articles and Journals on Crossref

The data we obtained by combining the articles in the DOAJ with Crossref's API indicates that more than 90% [fig. 2] of articles with a DOI on DOAJ are on Crossref.⁶

Figure 2. pie-chart

The graph in [fig. 3] shows that the distribution of articles on Crossref is consistent. On average, journals have more than 87% of their articles on Crossref. Journals with less than 50% of articles on Crossref have a median number of 136 articles with DOI. Of the over 17000 journals of the DOAJ, 12450 of them provided a DOI (about 70% of the journals in the DOAJ).

Presence on Crossref is consistent in journals from different fields, with over 80% in almost all of them; the highest percentages are found in the STM fields [fig. 4]. No significant outlier is found in articles from different years, except for the rise in recent years [fig. 5]. Most resources are journal articles, about 93.4% of DOAJ articles that are on Crossref.

⁶About 75% of the total number of articles in the batch we used had a DOI

Figure 3. violin-chart

Figure 4. bar-chart

Figure 5. RQ2 line-chart

There are differences between the journals’ countries of origin in the number of articles on Crossref. The negative outliers, shown in [fig. 6], appear to be from journals from many countries around the globe, with a lower percentage also in European countries.

DOAJ Journals	Median number of resources	Average number of resources	Average percentage of resources on Crossref per Journal
All Journals with more than 10 articles	149	469	87.6%
Journals with less than 50% of articles on Crossref	111	205	4%

Table 3. DOAJ Journals and Crossref - Journals with lower percentages of resources on Crossref tend to have a smaller number of resources overall

Figure 6. RQ2 line-chart

3.2 Metadata on DOAJ

Table 4 shows the data about dates in the DOAJ and its presence in Crossref. Several articles have a wrong date associated or do not have a date of publication; in these cases, the date presented is 0.0, 'my_year' or a date before 1900 (mainly 1400), the latter case we believe represents dates coming from a non-Gregorian calendar system. For most of these articles, there is a record on Crossref, with almost all of them on Crossref.

Set of Articles	Percentage on Crossref
All DOAJ articles	92.8%
Articles from DOAJ with bad date format	98.7%

Table 4. Articles with the date and with bad or unknown date format

3.3 Citation Data on Crossref

[fig. 7] shows that almost 70% of resources (of the types that, according to Crossref, have reference lists as recommended metadata) in DOAJ's dump have a reference list on Crossref. However, the distribution of this data is heterogeneous [fig. 3].

Figure 7. pie-chart

When analysing the yearly distribution of this datum, the median value is around 20%, with a growing trend for articles from recent years [fig. 5]. After being around 50% for articles published in the early 2010s, the availability of citation data grew up to more than 80% for articles published this year.

Between research fields, the presence of reference lists is higher in STM fields, with a lower percentage in fields related to the Humanities [fig. 8]. When looking at types, most of the articles (almost 95%) are journal articles, with the second highest being proceeding articles. Types did not show any particular behaviour, but were taken into account when analysing the presence of references.

In the case of the country of origin of the journals, there is a small number of countries that perform particularly well [fig. 9]; however, the distribution does not allow for a clear conclusion .

Of these items, about 20% of them have no DOI specified (we could not measure whether there is no DOI associated with it or if Crossref could not find a DOI) [fig. 10].

The distribution changes depending on the year (most recent articles have reference lists, with the number of articles with a DOI in their reference lists becoming prominent since 2002) [fig. 11], in

Crossref references list overview - by research field

Figure 8. bar-chart

Crossref references list overview - by country
The plot is showing Countries with more than 60% of reference list on Crossref

Figure 9. bar-chart

Percentage of DOIs registered on Crossref

Figure 10. pie-chart

References DOI overview over years.

Figure 11. line-chart

the research field (the number of references with a DOI is concentrated in STM fields). On the geographical side, it appears that journals from South Globe countries have a percentage of DOIs lower than the rest of the world [fig. 12].

Figure 12. stacked-bar-chart

About the entity responsible for asserting the DOI, the biggest factor is the publisher with around 60% of all references, while Crossref was able to assert 22% of the DOIs [fig. 10]. Beyond the raw percentage, there is a difference between the two in their scope; Crossref asserted most of the DOIs before 2015 [fig. 13] and for journals from Africa, North America, South America and Asia [fig. 14]. On the other hand, publishers of STM fields have higher involvement in publishing metadata, while in the Humanities the role of assertion is equal or Crossref’s crawler is more prominent[fig. 15].

Data shows that articles released after 2010 have more references asserted by their publishers rather than Crossref[fig. 13]. The presence of references varies also between rich and poor countries and between research fields; journals from STM have reference lists more often than journals from the Humanities.

4 DISCUSSION

From our results, we can answer our research questions and elaborate on them.

- **RQ1:** *How many articles published in the open access journals in DOAJ are included in Crossref?*

Reference assertion overview - by year.

Figure 13. histogram

Reference assertion overview - by continent.

Figure 14. stacked-bar-chart

Figure 15. stacked-bar-chart

Most articles in the DOAJ are on Crossref and they have very different degrees of metadata quality. One can even find some having limited information on DOAJ, like missing or wrong information about the date or a date in a non-Gregorian calendar format.

What this suggests is that most journals publish their metadata on Crossref; on the other hand, journals that have a lower percentage of articles on Crossref tend to have a lower number of articles overall.

We interpreted this information in this way:

1. Journals with less than 50% of articles on Crossref are smaller than average and have less attention to metadata;
2. Journals that have a lower number of DOIs associated with their articles have less attention to their metadata overall.

This problem, which emerged in Allen and Weber (2015), is crucial to the development and survival of these journals, as providing metadata is the main feature to make articles findable and, thus, impactful. Moreover, for the articles with alternative calendars from the Gregorian, we suggest that:

1. Instead of having just one date format, one could have multiple, preserving the multi-cultural perspective on dates and interoperability with articles following the Western date systems. As an example:

```
"date": [{
  "type": "gregorian"
  "year": 2022
  "month": 5
  "day": 6
}
{
  "type": "jalali"
  "year": 1401
  "month": 2
  "day": 16
}]
```

2. A cooperation between Crossref and DOAJ could be instrumental to insert in the dump better information about dates.

An effort in providing to small journals more guidance in providing metadata about their articles would also be beneficial.

The difference in fields is not as strong, but it should be noted that articles from journals in the STM fields have almost all their DOIs on Crossref, with lower percentages (around 80%) for articles in the Humanities.

A different explanation for the lack of metadata that should be explored is the presence in the DOAJ of articles from publishers who may not publish anymore and, as such, do not have an authority responsible for making available the metadata outside publishers. This hypothesis could be verified by combining data about journals with the data about journals. In this case, and for the general availability of metadata, the author her/himself should provide the metadata for the articles.

Another element that emerged in answering this question is the absence of about 21.7% of the journals in the DOAJ in our analysis, as they provided no DOI, to begin with. Currently, a persistent identifier is a necessity in guaranteeing the findability of resources (Cheby, 2016). Verifying the origin of this problem is beyond the scope of this paper.

- **RQ2:** *How many of these articles include information about their reference lists?*

While almost all of DOAJ's articles are on Crossref, the information about their reference list has gained attention in the open access publishing community only recently. This would be important to optimise research and findability verification of studies. The trend, in this case, is clear: the attention to specifying reference lists is a recent one, with the articles in the last decade having most of their references specified. An effort should be made to increase the number of older articles with reference lists as well as to cover the 30.9% of articles that have

them still unpublished. This should also involve articles belonging to journals mostly from South-globe countries and from SSH fields. This different behaviour in the way citations are made available has emerged from other studies like Martín-Martín et al. (2018b).

This difference in citation metadata might stem from the fact that the attention to open reference lists is still niche compared to the attention to other publicly available metadata. The upward trend in the specification of citation data is probably connected to the various initiatives for freeing the content of citation data in the 2010s, especially after the foundation of the Initiative for Open Citations⁷.

- **RQ3:** *How many references have a DOI specified?*

Most references provide a DOI. For older articles, the percentage of references with a DOI is understandably low, but thanks to Crossref's algorithm the percentage of references without doi is slightly below 30% in 2010. For more recent articles, the percentage has been going down steadily especially since the 2010s, reaching less than 20% after 2020. This can be expected by the fact that a retroactive action is needed to create DOIs for older articles, something that has a minor incentive compared to associating a DOI to a newer article. This might also lead newer articles to cite recent studies as older ones are not provided by DOIs. This discussion could be explored in future studies by also checking references' publication dates and see if our claim is correct, and supported by appropriate data.

The difference between research fields is also significant, with STM fields that have almost all their references with a DOI and most Humanities fields with a fraction of their references having a persistent ID.

The difference in the distribution of references between countries of provenance and in the distribution of reference DOIs may also be connected to the peripheral nature of scientific research in developing countries (Salager-Meyer, 2008); opening the metadata could be beneficial for African and South American journals to take a more central role in global research.

The difference between research fields is also significant, with STM fields that have almost all their references with a DOI and most Humanities fields with a fraction of their references having a persistent ID.

- **RQ4:** *How many of these DOIs have been specified by the publishers? And how many by Crossref?*

Crossref specifies most of the DOIs of articles' references before 2000; the growing attention by publishers to this issue has also significantly increased the importance of their role in specifying the DOIs, lately growing just shy of 60% of all references DOIs.

⁷<https://i4oc.org/>

Crossref is especially important for providing a DOI for older research papers' references and – still – has an important role in current research when providing a permanent identifier. From a geopolitical perspective, the role of Crossref in asserting reference DOIs is higher for African journals. Finally, there is a big difference between research fields, suggesting that the movement for opening citation data did not penetrate the Humanities as much. A possible explanation comes from the different roles of book publications in this field, a category of resource that is still minor in Crossref (Visser et al., 2021).

It could be interesting to see how the coverage in the reference lists' DOIs will evolve in the future and the responsibility of their assertion will be distributed among publishers and Crossref. The shape may change a lot even in a few years, as the recent, exponential growth of citations shows.

5 CONCLUSION

This study shows the state of metadata from articles in the DOAJ on Crossref and how the cooperation of the two services could be beneficial for the state of Open Access journals' metadata.

Moreover, it highlights multiple issues: the problem of journals with fewer DOIs and minimal metadata and the issue of disclosing reference lists from papers. While attention to this issue has been growing, there is still a lot to be done. In this context, Crossref's role should not be understated.

REFERENCES

- Ahlgren, P., Colliander, C., and Sjögårde, P. (2018). Exploring the relation between referencing practices and citation impact: A large-scale study based on Web of Science data. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 69(5):728–743.
- Allen, E. J. and Weber, R. K. (2015). An Exploration of Indexed and Non-Indexed Open Access Journals: Identifying Metadata Coding Variations. *Journal of Web Librarianship*, 9(2-3):65–84.
- Brembilla, D., Catizone, C., and Venditti, G. (2022a). La Chouffe Dataset. Version Number: 0.0.1 Type: dataset.
- Brembilla, D., Catizone, C., and Venditti, G. (2022b). La Chouffe Software. Language: en.
- Cheby, L. E. (2016). Open Access Metadata for Journals in Directory of Open Access Journals: Who, How, and What Scheme? *School of Information Student Research Journal*, 6(1).
- Chudlarský, T. and Dvořák, J. (2020). Can Crossref Citations Replace Web of Science for Research Evaluation? The Share of Open Citations. *Journal of Data and Information Science*, 5(4):35–42.
- Cioffi, A., Coppini, S., Massari, A., Moretti, A., Peroni, S., Santini, C., and Asadi, N. S. (2021). Identifying and correcting invalid citations due to DOI errors in Crossref data. Publisher: arXiv Version Number: 2.

- Eck, N.J.P. van; Waltman, L. (2021). Crossref as a source of open bibliographic metadata. In *Proceedings of the 18th international conference of the international society for scientometrics and informetrics*, pages 1169 – 1174.
- Gatten, R. (2010). A case study in reference list accuracy. *New Library World*, 111(1/2):16–25.
- Ghane, M. R., Niazmand, M. R., and Sabet Sarvestani, A. (2020). The citation advantage for open access science journals with and without article processing charges. *Journal of Information Science*, 46(1):118–130.
- Hendricks, G., Tkaczyk, D., Tkaczyk, D., Lin, J., Lin, J., and Feeney, P. (2020). Crossref: The sustainable source of community-owned scholarly metadata. *Quantitative Science Studies*.
- Jahn, N., Matthias, L., and Laakso, M. (2021). Transparency to hybrid open access through publisher-provided metadata: An article-level study of Elsevier. *arXiv:2102.04789 [cs]*. arXiv: 2102.04789.
- Laakso, M., Welling, P., Bukvova, H., Nyman, L., Björk, B.-C., and Hedlund, T. (2011). The Development of Open Access Journal Publishing from 1993 to 2009. *PLoS ONE*, 6(6):e20961.
- Martín-Martín, A., Costas, R., van Leeuwen, T., and Delgado López-Cózar, E. (2018a). Evidence of open access of scientific publications in Google Scholar: A large-scale analysis. *Journal of Informetrics*, 12(3):819–841.
- Martín-Martín, A., Orduna-Malea, E., Thelwall, M., and Delgado López-Cózar, E. (2018b). Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus: A systematic comparison of citations in 252 subject categories. *Journal of Informetrics*, 12(4):1160–1177.
- Panda, S. (2021). Open Access Indian Publications: An Empirical Study of DOAJ. *SRELS Journal of Information Management*, 58(3):187.
- Piwowar, H., Priem, J., Larivière, V., Alperin, J. P., Matthias, L., Norlander, B., Farley, A., West, J., and Haustein, S. (2018). The state of OA: a large-scale analysis of the prevalence and impact of Open Access articles. *PeerJ*, 6:e4375.
- Piwowar, H., Priem, J., and Orr, R. (2019). The Future of OA: A large-scale analysis projecting Open Access publication and readership. preprint, Scientific Communication and Education.
- Piwowar, H. A. and Vision, T. J. (2013). Data reuse and the open data citation advantage. *PeerJ*, 1:e175.
- Salager-Meyer, F. (2008). Scientific publishing in developing countries: Challenges for the future. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 7(2):121–132.
- Shotton, D. (2013). Publishing: Open citations. *Nature*, 502(7471):295–297.
- Visser, M., van Eck, N. J., and Waltman, L. (2021). Large-scale comparison of bibliographic data sources: Scopus, Web of Science, Dimensions, Crossref, and Microsoft Academic. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 2(1):20–41.
- Woelfle, M., Olliaro, P., and Todd, M. H. (2011). Open science is a research accelerator. *Nature Chemistry*, 3(10):745–748.